

SEARCH FOR INSECTICIDES. PART II

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Trichloroacetates of *o*-chlorophenol, *m*-chlorophenol, catechol, resorcinol and hydroquinone have been prepared.

It is necessary to have a grouping which confers lipid solubility and another one possessing toxicity, in the molecule of a good contact insecticide (Busvine, *Nature*, 1945, 156, 179). A number of esters of trichloroacetic acid and halogenated phenols have been prepared with this aim in view (Sen and Bhargava, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 277). In this paper, the preparation of trichloroacetates of *o*-chlorophenol, *m*-chlorophenol, catechol, resorcinol and hydroquinone have been described. The trichloroacetyl esters of *o*- and *m*-chlorophenols are colorless liquids and are obtained in nearly theoretical yields. The di-trichloroacetates of resorcinol, catechol and hydroquinone are not obtained in so good yields; these esters darken on exposure to light and the last two are very hygroscopic.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Sodium Salts of the Phenols.—The sodium salts of *o*-chlorophenol, *m*-chlorophenol, catechol and hydroquinone were prepared by adding an absolute alcoholic solution of the phenol to a solution of sodium ethoxide (equimolecular quantity) in absolute alcohol (15 c.c. for each g. of sodium). In the case of catechol and hydroquinone, the sodium salts separated out as crystalline precipitates, which were quickly filtered off, pressed and dried. In the case of *o*- and *m*-chlorophenols, the sodium derivatives could only be obtained after distilling off the excess of alcohol on an oil-bath at 125°-130°.

The sodium salt of resorcinol was prepared by adding a little less than the required amount of caustic soda, dissolved in a small quantity of water, to resorcinol, using phenolphthalein as the indicator. The solution was evaporated almost to dryness on a water-bath and left in a vacuum desiccator.

Condensation with Trichloroacetyl Chloride.—The sodium salt of the phenol was suspended in dry petrol-ether (40-50 c.c.) in a 250 c.c. pyrex flask attached to a reflux condenser; the flask was then cooled in ice and trichloroacetyl chloride ($1\frac{1}{2}$ to 2 times the calculated amount) added from the top of the condenser. The reaction was allowed to take place for $\frac{1}{2}$ to 1 hour in the cold; the contents of the flask were then refluxed over a water-bath for 2 to 3 hours and then left overnight. The sodium chloride formed was filtered off and well washed with petrol-ether. The petrol-ether was removed from the filtrate on a water-bath and the residual liquid distilled in vacuum on a metal-bath, when the trichloroacetate of the corresponding phenol was obtained. The trichloroacetates of *m*- and *o*-chlorophenols and the di-trichloroacetates of catechol, hydroquinone and resorcinol, thus prepared, are described in Table I.

TABLE I.

No.	Reactants		Yield.	Properties.	Formula.	Found (%)			Calculated (%)			
	Na salts of phenol.	CCl ₃ COO				B. p. of the ester.	C.	H.	Cl.	C.	H.	Cl.
I	10 g.	18 g.	86-88°/22mm	15 g.	Colorless liquid.	C ₈ H ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	34.77	1.45	51.52	35.04	1.46	51.83
II	5	9	119-122°/26	9	Colorless liquid.	C ₈ H ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	34.87	1.49	51.59	35.04	1.46	51.83
III	4.4	9	169-171°/18	8	Pale yellow liquid, solidifying on cooling in ice. Has a characteristic smell and turns deep green on keeping.	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₄ Cl ₆	29.62	1.16	53.40	29.92	1.00	53.16
IV	7.7	18.2	95°/5	8	Colorless liquid solidifying to white crystals on cooling in ice. Has very characteristic smell and turns deep brown on keeping; is very hygroscopic.	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₄ Cl ₆	29.67	1.06	53.01	29.92	1.00	53.16
V	6.6	18.2	95°/5	6.4	Colorless liquid with characteristic smell; turns red and then brown in a few months.	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₄ Cl ₆	29.56	1.08	52.79	29.92	1.00	53.16

I—Trichloroacetate of *o*-chlorophenol. II—Trichloroacetate of *m*-chlorophenol. III—Di-trichloroacetate of catechol. IV—Di-trichloroacetate of hydroquinone. V—Di-trichloroacetate of resorcinol.

The hydrolysis of the trichloroacetate of *o*-chlorophenol by alkali resulted in the formation of *o*-chlorophenol and trichloroacetic acid.

The insecticidal action of the compounds described in this paper, is under investigation.

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